

STYLUS SUPPORT STRUCTURE AND FUNCTION OF RADULAR TEETH IN CRYPTOCHITON STELLERI

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ABSTRACT

Biological materials exhibit complex hierarchical structures that are often multifunctional. Properties useful for engineering applications include structural stability, maintenance of directional flexibility, and channels for mineral transport. These materials are produced at ambient temperature and pressure, close to neutral pH, and represent an ideal model for lightweight, load bearing structural materials. Organisms use these materials for feeding by means of boring, grinding, and excavating. The *Cryptochiton stelleri* is a chiton species that takes advantage of a tube-like support pillar, called a stylus, to extend an ultra hard magnetic tooth away from a soft organic radula during rasping events. The stylus is stiff enough to transfer force from the radula base to the tooth, yet compliant enough to contour to rugged, rough surfaces due to a graded modulus along the length of the stylus. The spring like rotation of the ultrastructure and well defined regionalized mechanical properties on the micro- and nanoscale features account for the orientational versatility of the stylus. The regionalized mechanical properties in the stylus were measured with nanoindentation, and correspond to regions with distinct chemical signatures, identified by energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). The findings of this project will serve as a basis for biologically inspired composite materials with graded moduli, and work to effectively bridge hard and soft materials, potentially in machinery, biomedical devices, and robotic applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

Structural support materials traditionally incorporate heavy, stiff components. This is in contrast to natural design strategies, which are usually lightweight, compliant materials. Whether the material is used to join structures, extend a piece of tooling equipment, or operate at a specific loading condition, the type of connection used can either be stiff to control a fixed angle or compliant to allow

maneuverability. Structural support materials typically used in load bearing applications like steel, concrete, and clays are prone to brittle failure, heavy, and thus energy intensive during use and transport. The importance of reducing the amount of energy used to produce, transport, and ultimately utilize structural materials demands that we consider alternative designs in order to maximize resources and improve the efficiency of modern materials. Biological organisms demonstrate a high level of control at the micro and nanoscale to produce extremely lightweight materials that can inspire a new generation of materials that combine beneficial properties.

Figure 1 A. Overview of *Cryptochiton stelleri* suctioned to aquarium glass. B. Schematic of molluscan radula during feeding. C. Complete chiton radula. D. Teeth and styli on radular membrane. E-H. Isolated tooth and stylus. E. Front view. F. Rear view. G. Outer profile view. H. Inner profile view.

Biological organisms have developed complex, hierarchical composites with graded chemical and mechanical properties that allow them to transfer force and interact with their immediate environment. These organisms create composite materials that incorporate regio-specific mineral phases into an organic framework that exhibit a balance of material properties that are usually at odds with each other (compliant and rigid). Lightweight, multifunctional biological support materials prompt the development of structures that can mimic the precise control of regional mechanics of natural design strategies that are effective and not usually found in current engineering materials. An example of one such material is found in the molluscan radula of the *Cryptochiton stelleri*, an armored polyplachaphora.

The teeth of chitons are arranged in parallel rows on a tongue like feeding organ called a radula. The radula of *Cryptochiton stelleri*, the largest species of chiton, contains more than 70 rows of tricuspid teeth affixed to an organic membrane. The chiton uses these radular teeth to scrape algae from rocks. The radula displays active mineralization, with the degree of mineralization increasing from a completely non-mineralized structure consisting of alpha-chitin at the posterior end to a fully mineralized tooth at the anterior end.

The polysaccharide fibers found in the tooth are also found in the radular stylus, the tubular structure that supports and extends the tooth above the surface of the radular belt. The stylus is particularly interesting because it is a natural structure that strategically controls mineralization across nanoscale interfaces to create microscale regimes with drastically different mechanical properties. The proximity of the stylus and tooth is short, creating a narrow interface between two objects with drastically different material properties. These micro-regimes cooperate to create an overall structure that provides a rigid support and compliant flexible tether that allows for angular and rotational freedom during rasping events.

Compared to the magnetite teeth, which constitute the hardest known biomineral, the stylus is relatively soft, however within the stylus there are regions that display higher elastic modulus and hardness including the trailing edge and the posterior side of the leading edge. The majority of the stylus is composed of alpha-chitin and specific regions are mineralized with amorphous calcium phosphate and iron phosphate.

Although epithelial tissue at the tooth surface is involved with the mineralization of the tooth cusp, it is believed that the stylus provides an alternate route for element delivery. Chiton's flexoglossate radula uses musculature to laterally rotate the teeth around buccal cartilage with each rasp, demonstrating a higher degree of tooth orientation control compared to other iron mineralizing stereoglossate molluscan radula found in limpets, which do not have this complex anterior buccal musculature. Chiton with tricuspid teeth do not dig deeply in the substrate, rather they rake rocky surfaces to scrape larger algal structure from the surface, as is gleaned from unworn edges between cusp denticles. The tessellate arrangement of the styli and marginal teeth along the radular belt form an interlocking network that helps to distribute the stresses applied during rasping. It has been observed that fiber orientation helps control the wear and fracture properties in the tooth, but the manner in which the fiber orientation influences the properties in the stylus has not been reported. Unicuspid and tricuspid teeth have different microstructures, trough shaped and rod shapes respectively, but what can be said about the fiber structures of these types of teeth, and how those fibers propagate through the stylus and through the junction zone? In stage III of tooth mineralization, after magnetite shell formation, the core is isolated from epithelial tissue at the surface. The junction zone itself has been identified as a focal point for elemental accumulation prior to core mineralization, but the role of the fiber architecture has yet to be determined. The only route for stage IV core mineralization requires ion transport across the junction from the stylus. The presence of amorphous iron granules found within stylus pore canal, similar to the environment found on the surface of the tooth, supports mineralization of the teeth and stylus on two fronts.

2 RESULTS

2.1 Laminated fiber sheets within stylus

To understand the internal structure, fractured sections were prepared along the long axis and transverse sections along the length of fully mineralized styli. From a transverse section, fiber sheets are measured to be 2.2 - 2.7 μ m thick, and a longitudinal fracture shows the laminated fiber sheets running the length of the stylus. These sheets appear to run up along the leading edge, around the junction zone, and back down the trailing edge of the stylus as is shown in the micrograph below. Serial transverse sections reveal a transition in the macro-morphology in the stylus from a thin strip at the base of the radula, to an expanded flanged tube above the pore canal opening. From the serial transverse cross sections, it is evident that the stylus is rotating approximately 90 degrees from the original stylus base orientation. The transverse cross section measurement at the stylus elbow is 350 μ m by 350 μ m. The measurement of the stylus at the base is 350 μ m by 100 μ m. The measurement of the stylus below the junction zone is 400 μ m by 250 μ m. The extent of rotation was observed using an overview SEM micrograph of the radula with styli arranged below.

2.2 Micromechanical Analysis

Nanoindentation was performed on polished longitudinal and transverse cross sections to identify the modulus and hardness of the stylus structure. Above the stylus elbow, discrete bands of material

are located with distinct mechanical properties.

Starting at the stylus leading edge there is a band 12 μ m thick with modulus of 10.5GPa and hardness of 0.6GPa. Following that is a band 15 μ m thick with modulus of 9.5GPa and hardness of 0.55GPa. The next band, which is the side of leading edge closest to the stylus canal, is 27 μ m thick with a modulus of 11-12GPa and hardness of 0.6-0.65GPa.

The stylus pore canal is 32 μ m wide with modulus of 8.5-9.5GPa and hardness of 0.4GPa.

Figure 2. Polished transverse stylus cross section (left). Modulus map (middle). Hardness map (right).

Nano indentation at the trailing edge shows there are still bands with different mechanical properties, but the transition between the two tends to be somewhat graded. Following the pore canal, the first band in the trailing edge is approximately 16 μ m thick with modulus of 11GPa and hardness of 0.55GPa. The Band closest to the surface of the trailing edge is 15 μ m with modulus of 12GPa and hardness of 0.6GPa.

The highest values were found in the band closest to the trailing edge surface has a region up to 100 μ m below the junction zone that is 30 μ m thick with a modulus of of 14GPa and hardness of 0.7GPa

2.3 Regional Analysis

Fiber sheets curve through and around the junction zone. After detaching the tooth cusp from stylus, a small rim of magnetite remains attached above the junction zone on the leading edge of the stylus. Using SEM to interrogate the magnetite remnants on the stylus, periodic grooves are observed traversing the magnetite surface. The highly aligned grooves are 150-200nm thick, and are spaced 1-3 μ m apart. In the same sample above the junction zone outer cusp, there are highly aligned protrusions from the junction zone, about 2 μ m thick. A longitudinal fracture of the tooth as it is attached to the stylus was examined at the interface between the leading edge at the junction zone with BSE microscopy. Alpha-chitin sheets extend through the junction zone into the leading edge of the tooth shell and are mineralized with magnetite. The transition from tooth to stylus occurs over an interface that is ~2 μ m thick.

2.4 Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy

Quantitative elemental analysis of the stylus was performed using energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). A false colored distribution map of Iron (blue), Oxygen (green), and Calcium (red) in a polished longitudinal section encompassing the junction zone is presented in figure 3. In this figure it is clear that the stylus is highly regionalized, with banding appearing in the elemental distributions of Iron, Calcium, and Oxygen. It is well established that the core-shell structure of the tooth is Iron phosphate and Iron oxide that has sharp, well-defined interfaces. The stylus, in a longitudinal section is also divided into regions with fairly distinct interfaces at and below the junction zone. The junction zone is the border between the tooth and stylus. From these EDS maps, the stylus was divided into 5 vertical bands (Leading edge surface, leading edge median, inner leading edge, inner trailing edge, trailing edge surface). In the leading edge surface, Iron and Oxygen have the strongest correlation. Leading edge surface contains Iron and Phosphorous, while the inner leading edge contains Iron, Oxygen, and Phosphorous. The leading edge median contains Phosphorous and Sulfur. The inner trailing edge contains Calcium, Oxygen, and Phosphorous. The trailing edge surface contains Iron, Phosphorous, and Oxygen. The Iron and Phosphate bands stretch down the stylus at least as far as the

stylus elbow. Just below the ridges on the surface of the trailing edge, the stylus shows a strong Sulfur signature. Virtually the entire lower stylus shows a significant concentration of Sulfur.

A line scan across the stylus shows abrupt compositional changes between bands, but a line scan along the length of the stylus shows a graded concentration along each band.

Figure 3 Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy False Color Maps at the Junction Zone (right), and an overview with multiple styli and teeth (right), both are longitudinal sections.

3 DISCUSSION

Future engineering structures utilized in excavation, robotics, aerospace, and transportation will require materials for structural reinforcement, flexible, and low weight for reduced energy consumption and reduced wear and tear on central chassis for heavy pieces of equipment. Although stiffness is a critical aspect in a structural support material, flexibility is needed to navigate, adapt, and contour to unexpected pressures or contact points. Generally, in contemporary engineering materials, stiffness and flexibility are mutually exclusive. Natural materials, however, utilize highly regionalized composite structures to achieve a combination of both properties in a single component, a feature exemplified in the chiton stylus. While the stylus must be stiff enough to transfer force from the radular belt to the tooth and substrate, it must also be flexible enough to adjust to pressure from unexpected contacts, or to contour to substrates with irregular or uneven surfaces experienced during rasping events. Through ultrastructural analysis and finite element modeling of the stresses imparted on chiton styli during rasping, we observe how the organism has evolved features to act as a tether to the radular belt and transfer force to the tooth and substrate.

3.1 Bulk Features

The stylus can be split into two parts, the upper and lower stylus. The transition occurs at the elbow where there is a connection between the major lateral teeth and the marginal lateral teeth approximately halfway up the length of the stylus. The lower stylus is comprised of a ribbon like laminate that stands upright, with the thinner edge resting on the radular membrane. Halfway up the stylus, the stylus of the major lateral tooth connects to the supporting marginal lateral teeth. It is at this connection that the marginal lateral tooth obstructs the path of the ribbon-like lower stylus. The lower end of the ribbon that rests on the radular membrane changes position laterally around the marginal tooth, thereby causing the entire stylus structure to rotate.

The continuous fiber sheets that form the stylus exhibit a rotation along the length that gives the stylus a spring-like appearance. The rotation is an outward twist of about 90 degrees. At the base of the stylus, the tube like structure appears to be composed of two laminates flush against each other like

a ribbon standing upright on the radular membrane. As the stylus approaches the pore canal opening, the two halves separate, thereby creating a cavity, in which fluids from the radular sac enter and inflate the stylus. The cavity changes the stylus morphology from a ribbon to a tubular structure above the pore canal opening. It is above this opening that the stylus begins to lift off of the radular membrane and starts to twist about the long axis.

The stylus is interesting because it is both stiff and flexible, and accomplishes this without implementing joints or musculature. The stylus and tooth lend themselves to an overall “C” shape, which has been shown to distribute forces throughout the structure, rather than concentrating the force at the tip as observed in a straight morphology. The 90-degree twist along the length of the tube allows for increased flexibility about the axis of rotation. In the case of the chiton, the rotation of the stylus along the length is counter to the rasp rotation of the stylus along the substrate. This combination of rotations in the structure and motion of the stylus aligns the tooth denticles in an ideal position for maximum contact with the substrate. The twist also sets a preload on the tooth like a tensioner, so that during rasping events, a pulling force at the base of the stylus will result in a delayed response by the tooth. If the force applied by the preloaded stylus is greater than the force across the substrate, a successful rasp will occur. If the force applied by the preload is not great enough to overcome the friction forces offered by the substrate, then the tooth is able to rotate negatively until the rotation of the base of the stylus allows the tooth to clear the obstructing surface.

The ridges located below the junction zone on the trailing and outer edge of the stylus occur in the area of the highest mineral concentration, as well as highest hardness and stiffness. These ridges on the upper stylus are believed to serve two purposes. 1. To provide structural rigidity to the tube-like structure. 2. To serve as an outlet for expansion should the stylus swell during inflation during mineral transport by hydraulic pressure. Ridged structures in have been found to increase the surface to volume ratio so as not to apply stress to the epidermis during swelling, while also increasing the flexure stiff of higher aspect ratio object. Having a plicate surface, as solution is absorbed or pumped through the pore canal, stylus volume increases, rib bases merely spread apart, increasing the rib's volume without requiring an increase in surface area. The stylus can change volume but not surface area so there is no damage to epidermis or hypodermis. Finite element modeling, performed in this study, shows that the ridged tube structure has a higher flexure modulus than that of a tube with the same surface area without ridges. By strategically reinforcing areas that are prone to higher stresses, the chiton stylus uses small changes in bulk morphology to improve mechanical performance.

The ridged structures are able to selectively mineralize along concentric alpha-chitin fiber sheets that run along the length of the stylus and into the tooth. These sheets are typically mineralized with amorphous iron phosphate at the junction zone and on the stylus trailing edge. The junction zone itself is composed of amorphous calcium phosphate, and the lower leading edge of the stylus is primarily sulfated alpha chitin. SEM of these sheets in the lower stylus region shows straight laminated sheets aligned along the long axis of the stylus. However, at the junction zone, SEM shows the fiber sheets curve around and conform to the junction zone (or bend around and the resulting surface forms the junction zone). The layers of fiber sheets may be the reason the interface between the tooth core and the stylus is so sharp, only 2um thick. In freeze-fractured styli, SEM shows that the fiber sheets are also around 2um thick in the elbow region. The sharpness between interfaces is very tight in the three bands of the stylus leading edge, around 200um. A point of interest is that the bands in the leading edge is that they connect at the junction zone and taper as they move towards the lower stylus.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The stylus in the radula of *Cryptochiton stelleri* is an example of a modified mineralized hydrostatic skeletal system that demonstrates an excellent integration of stiff and flexible components. With this combination of material properties, the stylus is able to maintain a firm connection to the radular belt and tooth cusp, and transfer force from the radular musculature to abrade the substrate with a consistently applied force, without the danger of breaking off the tooth. This complex fiber reinforced support structure is lightweight, stiff, and flexible. The curvature and rotation of the stylus allows for non-localized stress distributions throughout the material. Selectively mineralized bands in the upper stylus form regions that perform well under tension on the leading edge and compression on

the trailing edge. The mineral transport channels in the stylus add to the multi functionality of the structure. Engineers that adopt this type of support structure can modify the channels to transport other substances through the stylus, such as coolant, lubricant, a self-healing fluid, or antibacterial agent. Utilizing the design of this natural composite, as well as a bio-inspired synthesis method, will be advantageous where weight reduction is an important factor.

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